

VK4EMM amatur radio station description for Eclipse 14 October 2023

Band	Modes	TX Radio	TX Freq offset	RX Radio	Oscillator	Software	Spectral width w50 Captured	Computer	Filters	Antenna	Call	Grid
20m TX	FST4W-120	QDX 2 Watts	1425		External GPSDO Bodnar	WSJT-X 2.6.1		Raspberry pi 5 Debian Bullseye	20m BPF	Dipole 6.5m high Horizontal	VK4EMM	QG62lr
40m RX	FST4W-120 and WSPR-2			RSPduo sdrplay 200703E532	External GPSDO Bodnar	SparkSDR 2.0.955	Yes	Intel NUC Win 11 VM	Before preamp: 2.6 MHz HPF 20m Band Stop 40m Band pass	Loop 5m high Vertical (see photo)	VK4EMM	QG62lr
15m RX	FST4W-120 and WSPR-2			RSPduo sdrplay 1809015132	External GPSDO Bodnar	SparkSDR 2.0.955	Yes	Intel NUC Win 11 VM	Before pre-amp: 2.6 MHz HPF 20m Band Stop 15m Band pass	Dipole 6.5m high Horizontal	VK4EMM	QG62lr
10m RX	FST4W-120 and WSPR-2			RSP1A sdrplay 19031D7096	Internal TCXO	SparkSDR 2.0.955	Yes	Intel NUC Win 11 VM	Before pre-amp: 2.6 MHz HPF 10m Band pass	Dipole 6.5m high Horizontal	VK4EMM	QG62lr

Logs uploaded 10m
10m_fst4w.txt (inc w50)
10m_wspr-2.txt
10m_spots.json

Logs uploaded 15m
15m_fst4w.txt (inc w50)
15m_wspr-2.txt
15m_spots.json

Logs uploaded 40m
40m_fst4w.txt (inc w50)
40m_wspr-2.txt
40m_spots.json